

Fabrication of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film for detection of H₂S gas

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ABSTRACT

In present work, Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick films are fabricated to investigate its gas response towards hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) gas. Pure SmFeO₃ powder is prepared by sol-gel method and thick films of SmFeO₃ are prepared by screen printing technique. Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick films are prepared by dipping pure SmFeO₃ thick films in 0.1 M cobalt chloride solution for 5 min followed by firing at 500°C. Morphology and elemental composition of both pure and Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick films are studied by Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) and Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDAX) techniques respectively. Gas response of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film towards 50 ppm H₂S gas is measured at different operating temperatures from room temperature to 400°C. Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film exhibited maximum gas response (3.24) at 200°C. Gas sensing mechanism and temperature dependence of H₂S gas response are discussed in details.

Keywords: - Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film, Dipping technique, Gas response, Optimal operating temperature, Adsorption.

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing need for environmental monitoring has stimulated considerable research on solid-state gas sensors based on semiconductor metal oxides. Materials such as ZnO, TiO₂, SnO₂, and their composites are well known for their application in solid-state gas sensors [1–3]. Perovskite-type oxides with the general formula ABO₃ have also been extensively investigated for solid state gas sensor due to their highly tunable physical and chemical properties [4–6]. Rare-earth orthoferrite such as LaFeO₃ and SmFeO₃ have been reported to exhibit excellent sensing performance toward both oxidizing and reducing gases [7–10]. SmFeO₃ is a promising p-type rare-earth orthoferrite that has been widely studied for the detection of oxidizing gases [9-10]. Its key advantages include p-type electrical conductivity, high oxygen-ion mobility, and strong catalytic activity toward oxidizing gases. The properties of SmFeO₃ can be effectively tailored by doping at either the A-site or B-site of the perovskite structure. Such modifications introduce structural defects and oxygen vacancies, which significantly influence its gas-sensing behavior. One effective approach to generate additional oxygen vacancies is the incorporation of oxidizing or reducing elements into SmFeO₃, which can be achieved through doping or surface modification (dipping) methods. Dopants such as Co, Ce, and Ni have been explored for the modification of SmFeO₃ [11-13]. Cobalt, being a reducible element, can induce a higher concentration of oxygen vacancies when introduced into pure SmFeO₃. In cobalt-doped SmFeO₃, each Co²⁺ ion contributes one electron, and the resulting cobalt misfit effectively acts as an oxygen vacancy [11]. However, since the Co–O bond is weaker than the Fe–O bond, chemical stability issues may arise under reducing gas environments. Therefore, the controlled addition of cobalt to pristine SmFeO₃ is essential to balance enhanced conductivity with structural stability. R. C. Michel reported the synthesis and characterization of SmCoO₃ for enhanced gas-sensing applications [14]. Enhanced ethanol sensing performance of SmFe_{0.7}Co_{0.3}O₃ was also reported by Ma Zhao *et al.* [11]. In our previous work, ammonia gas sensing properties of pure and Co- modified SmFeO₃ thick films (dipping time 1 min, 3 min and 5 min) were reported [15]. It was observed that, Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film (dipping time 3 min) exhibited excellent ammonia gas sensing properties as compared to other samples. In present work, gas response of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film (dipping time 5 min) towards H₂S gas is investigated.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Preparation of thick films

Pure nanocrystalline SmFeO₃ powder was prepared by sol-gel method. SmFeO₃ thick films were then

formed onto the glass substrate by screen printing technique. Details of sol-gel method and screen printing techniques were described in previous publications [12]. For surface modification, 0.1 M aqueous cobalt chloride solution was prepared and SmFeO₃ thick film was dipped into this solution for 5 min and then fired for 30 min at 500°C.

2.2 Characterization techniques

X-Ray Diffraction pattern of pure SmFeO₃ powder was obtained from PW 3071 powder diffractometer. The morphology of thick film was studied by Field Effect Scanning Electron Microscope (JSM- 7610F, JEOL Japan) operated at 15 kV. The elemental analysis of the films was carried out by the Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDAX) integrated to FE-SEM.

2.3 Gas sensing measurements

The gas response of Co surface modified SmFeO₃ thick film was studied in static gas sensing set-up. The operating temperature was varied from room temperature to 400°C and resistance of thick film was measured first in air and then in presence of fixed concentration (50 ppm) of target gas like liquid petroleum gas (LPG), carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrogen (H₂), chlorine (Cl₂) and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S). For p-type SMO, gas response is expressed as (R_g/R_a) where R_g and R_a represents resistance of semiconducting material in target gas and in air respectively [12-13].

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 XRD study

XRD pattern of SmFeO₃ powder prepared by sol-gel method is presented and explained in our earlier publications [15]. Obtained XRD pattern confirmed that as prepared SmFeO₃ powder has perovskite phase with orthorhombic symmetry and Pnma space group [10-11]. Narrow and sharp peaks indicated crystalline nature of powder. The average crystallite size calculated using Scherrer's formula is 50.08 nm.

3.2 FE-SEM study

Fig- 1: FE-SEM micrograph of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film [16].

FE-SEM micrograph of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film is shown in Fig. 1. Large numbers of SmFeO₃ grains are present indicating the porous nature of the film. Particles are irregular in shape and some particles are agglomerated. Co particles are dispersed on basic SmFeO₃ structure and can be confirmed in the EDAX micrograph. Therefore this film favors the adsorption and desorption processes in gas sensing mechanism.

3.3 EDAX study

Fig- 2: EDAX image of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film [16].

Fig. 2 is the EDAX spectrum of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film. It reveals the presence of Co on the film along with Sm, Fe and O. Further, no other element is observed in EDAX spectrum which means purity of sample.

3.3 H₂S gas sensing study

Fig- 3: Temperature dependence of gas response for Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film towards 50 ppm H₂S. Gas response of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film towards 50 ppm H₂S gas is measured at different operating temperatures from room temperature to 400°C. The temperature dependence of H₂S gas response of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 shows that initially, response towards 50 ppm H₂S increases with increase in operating temperature. At 200°C, maximum response (3.24) is obtained. But later on response decreases with further increase in temperature. Thus, Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film has optimal operating temperature 200°C at which its response towards 50 ppm H₂S gas becomes 3.24. This type of temperature dependence of gas response and gas sensing mechanism can be explained as follows.

The gas response is related to the adsorption of oxygen species in air and surface reactions of target gas

molecules with adsorbed oxygen. In ambient air, oxygen species from air are adsorbed on oxygen deficient surface of SmFeO₃ sensor. These adsorbed oxygen species extract electrons from bulk SmFeO₃ due to their strong electron affinity and highly reactive atomic or molecular species O_2^- , $2O^-$ and O^{2-} depending on temperature are

obtained [15]. Therefore, hole-accumulation layer is formed near the surface and sensor resistance decreases. When H₂S gas is introduced in chamber, surface reactions occur between H₂S gas molecules and the active oxygen species resulting in the decomposition of H₂S gas molecules along with emission of electrons. In Co-modified SmFeO₃ based sensor, Co²⁺ ion can also extract electron during electron transfer. Therefore, Co misfits also act as oxygen deficiency to adsorb oxygen from air.

At lower operating temperature, rate of surface reaction is low because H₂S gas molecules do not have sufficient thermal energy to react with oxygen species and hence sensor response is low. At 200^oC, the rate of surface reaction is high so that maximum number of H₂S gas molecules interact with maximum oxygen species and hence sensor response becomes maximum. But if temperature is further increased, gas diffusion near the surface decreases and sensor response decreases. The surface reaction of H₂S gas with adsorbed

oxygen species can be expressed as [17]

4. CONCLUSIONS

Pure SmFeO₃ thick films are modified by dipping technique and characterized by FE-SEM and EDAX techniques. As fabricated Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick films showed maximum response (3.24) towards 50 ppm H₂S gas at 200^oC. Thus Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film can be a potential candidate for H₂S gas sensor. It would be interesting to investigate selectivity, stability and response-recovery time of Co-modified SmFeO₃ thick film.

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